

$\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^* g\alpha}$ - Closed Sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

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Abstract. In neutrosophic topological spaces, the notion of neutrosophic $\alpha b^* g\alpha$ -closed sets, neutrosophic $\alpha b^* g\alpha$ -border, and neutrosophic $\alpha b^* g\alpha$ -frontier are described and their properties are discussed. The connection between neutrosophic $\alpha b^* g\alpha$ -frontier and neutrosophic $\alpha b^* g\alpha$ -border are established

Keywords: $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^* g\alpha}$ -closed sets, $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^* g\alpha}$ -border, $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^* g\alpha}$ -frontier.

1. Introduction

Neutrosophic sets is a generalisation of Atanassov's [4] intuitionistic fuzzy sets and Zadeh's [20] fuzzy sets, and were first proposed by Smarandache [17] [18]. It also takes into account the membership functions for falsehood, indeterminacy, and truth. In a number of disciplines, including probability, algebra, control theory, topology, etc., Smarandache introduced the neutrosophic idea in response to fuzzy sets and intuitionistic fuzzy sets' inability to handle indeterminacy-membership functions. Neutrosophic set based notions were later introduced by Alblowi et al. [1]. In the past 20 years, numerous scholars have utilised these potent ideas to put forth numerous topological hypotheses. A novel idea in neutrosophic topological spaces was proposed by Salama and Alblowi [14]. It gives a brief overview of neutrosophic topology, which is a generalisation of Chang's [6] and Coker's [5] intuitionistic fuzzy topology.

In the subject of neutrosophic topological spaces, Salama et al., [11–13] presented the generalisation of neutrosophic sets, neutrosophic crisp sets, and neutrosophic closed sets. Salama et al., [13] proposed a few neutrosophic continuous functions as an initial set of continuous functions in neutrosophic topology. In addition, a number of scholars have defined a number of

closed sets in neutrosophic topology, including generalised neutrosophic closed sets [7] in neutrosophic topological spaces, neutrosophic α -closed sets [3], neutrosophic αg -closed sets [10], and neutrosophic b -closed sets [8]. Neutrosophic $b^*g\alpha$ -closed sets were defined by S. Saranya and M. Vigneshwaran [15]. In order to establish a connection between the operators of neutrosophic interior and neutrosophic closure, Iswarya and Bageerathi [9] introduced a novel notion of neutrosophic frontier operator and neutrosophic semi-frontier operator. $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -closed sets are new closed sets defined in topological spaces by Suthi Keerthana K, Vigneshwaran M, and Vidyanani L [19]. These sets have been used to define various topological functions, such as continuous functions, irresolute functions, and homeomorphic functions with certain separable axioms.

This paper presents the idea of neutrosophic $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -closed sets in neutrosophic topological spaces and examines their characteristics as well as how they relate to other known characters. The concepts in neutrosophic $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -interior, neutrosophic $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -closure, neutrosophic $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -border, and neutrosophic $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -frontier are examined. Neutrosophic topological spaces have a relationship between the neutrosophic $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -border and the neutrosophic $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -frontier, along with associated features.

2. Preliminaries

The basic definitions which are used in the next section are referred from the references [14], [3], [7], [16], [10], [2], [15].

3. $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - Closed Sets

Definition 3.1. Let $\mathcal{N}E$ be a subset of a $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$. Then $\mathcal{N}E$ is called

- a neutrosophic $\alpha b^*g\alpha$ -closed set ($\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}\text{-CS}$) if $\mathcal{N}_\alpha \text{cl}(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ whenever $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ and \mathcal{V} is a neutrosophic $b^*g\alpha$ -open set in (\mathbb{X}, τ) .

Example 3.2. Let $\mathbb{X} = \{na, nb, nc\}$ and the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{S}$, $\mathcal{N}L$ and $\mathcal{N}M$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{N}L = \{ \langle nx, (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.4, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.2, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \},$$

$$\mathcal{N}M = \{ \langle nx, (t0.7, i0.3, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.3, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.2, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \},$$

Then the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}$, $\tau = \{ \mathcal{N}0, \mathcal{N}L, \mathcal{N}M, \mathcal{N}1 \}$, which are $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{O}\mathcal{S}$ in the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$.

If $\mathcal{N}N = \{ \langle nx, (t0.5, i0.8, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.8, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.9, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \}$, and

$$\mathcal{N}E = \{ \langle nx, (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \}$$

Then the complements of $\mathcal{N}L$, $\mathcal{N}M$, $\mathcal{N}N$ and $\mathcal{N}E$ are

$$\mathcal{N}\bar{L} = \{ \langle nx, (t0.7, i0.7, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.4), (t0.7, i0.8, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \},$$

$$\mathcal{N}\bar{M} = \{ \langle nx, (t0.5, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.8, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \},$$

$$\mathcal{N}\bar{N} = \{ \langle nx, (t0.7, i0.2, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.2, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.1, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}\overline{E} = \{ \langle nx, (t0.7, i0.7, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \}$$

Hence $\mathcal{N}N$ is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{OS} , $\mathcal{N}\overline{N}$ is a $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} , $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} , $\mathcal{N}\overline{E}$ is a $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{OS} of $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(E) = \{ \langle nx, (t0.5, i0.3, 0.7), (t0.6, i0.3, 0.7), (t0.5, i0.3, 0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \}$ which is contained in $\mathcal{N}N$. That is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{N}N$.

Remark 3.3. Let $\mathcal{N}A$ be a subset of $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$, then $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - $\mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}A)$ is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ -open in (\mathbb{X}, τ) .

Theorem 3.4. In $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$, every \mathcal{NCS} is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{OS} in \mathbb{X} .

$\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is \mathcal{NCS} , $\mathcal{N}cl(\mathcal{N}E) = \mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. But $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{N}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, which implies $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} .

The converse is not true.

Example 3.5. Let $\mathbb{X} = \{na, nb, nc\}$ and the \mathcal{NS} , $\mathcal{N}L$ and $\mathcal{N}M$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{N}L = \{ \langle nx, (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.4, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.2, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \},$$

$$\mathcal{N}M = \{ \langle nx, (t0.7, i0.3, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.3, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.2, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \},$$

Then the \mathcal{NT} , $\tau = \{ \mathcal{N}0, \mathcal{N}L, \mathcal{N}M, \mathcal{N}1 \}$ and the complement of \mathcal{NS} of $\mathcal{N}L$ and $\mathcal{N}M$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{N}\overline{L} = \{ \langle nx, (t0.7, i0.7, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.4), (t0.7, i0.8, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \},$$

$$\mathcal{N}\overline{M} = \{ \langle nx, (t0.5, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.8, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \},$$

$$\text{If } \mathcal{N}E = \{ \langle nx, (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X} \},$$

Then $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} but it is not a \mathcal{NCS} of $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}cl(\mathcal{N}E) = \mathcal{N}\overline{M}$ which is not equal to $\mathcal{N}E$.

Theorem 3.6. In $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$, every \mathcal{N}_{α} - \mathcal{CS} is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{OS} in \mathbb{X} .

$\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is \mathcal{N}_{α} - \mathcal{CS} , $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) = \mathcal{N}E$. But $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} .

The converse is not true.

Example 3.7. From the example 3.4, the $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} but it is not a \mathcal{N}_{α} - \mathcal{CS} of $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$. $\therefore \mathcal{N}cl(\mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}cl(E))) = \mathcal{N}\overline{M}$ which is not equal to $\mathcal{N}E$.

Theorem 3.8. In $\mathcal{NTS}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$, every $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{OS} in \mathbb{X} .

\therefore Every $\mathcal{N}_{*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{OS} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{OS} , \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{OS} .

$\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha b^*g\alpha}$ - \mathcal{CS} , $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. But $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq_{\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}} cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, which implies

$\mathcal{N}bcl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. $\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -CS.

The converse is not true.

Example 3.9. Let $\mathbb{X} = \{na, nb, nc\}$ and the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{S}$, $\mathcal{N}L$ and $\mathcal{N}M$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{N}L = \{\langle nx, (t0.6, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.2, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}M = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.3, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.3, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.2, f0.4) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\},$$

Then $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}$, $\tau = \{\mathcal{N}0, \mathcal{N}L, \mathcal{N}M, \mathcal{N}1\}$ and the complement of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{S}$ of $\mathcal{N}L$ and $\mathcal{N}M$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{N}\bar{L} = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.7, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.8, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}\bar{M} = \{\langle nx, (t0.5, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.4, i0.8, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}N = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.7, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.3, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\}$$

$$\text{If } \mathcal{N}E = \{\langle nx, (t0.6, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.7, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\}$$

Then $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -CS but it is not a $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.3, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.3, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\}$ which is not contained in $\mathcal{N}N$.

Theorem 3.10. In $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$, every $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS is \mathcal{N}_{gs} -CS.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{O}\mathcal{S}$ in \mathbb{X} .

\therefore Every $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{O}\mathcal{S}$ is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS, \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS, $\mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. But $\mathcal{N}_s cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, which implies $\mathcal{N}_s cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. $\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is \mathcal{N}_{gs} -CS.

The converse is not true.

Example 3.11. Let $\mathbb{X} = \{na, nb, nc\}$ and the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{S}$, $\mathcal{N}L$ and $\mathcal{N}M$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{N}L = \{\langle nx, (t0.6, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.2, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}M = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.3, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.3, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.4) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\},$$

Then $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}$, $\tau = \{\mathcal{N}0, \mathcal{N}L, \mathcal{N}M, \mathcal{N}1\}$ and the complement of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{S}$ of $\mathcal{N}L$ and $\mathcal{N}M$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{N}\bar{L} = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.7, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.8, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}\bar{M} = \{\langle nx, (t0.5, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.4, i0.3, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}N = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.7, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.3, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\}$$

$$\text{If } \mathcal{N}E = \{\langle nx, (t0.6, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.7, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\}$$

Here $\mathcal{N}E$ is \mathcal{N}_{gs} -CS but it is not a $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.3, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.3, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\}$ which is not contained in $\mathcal{N}N$.

Theorem 3.12. In $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$, every $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS is \mathcal{N}_{gp} -CS.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{O}\mathcal{S}$ in \mathbb{X} .

\therefore Every $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{O}\mathcal{S}$ is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS, \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS. $\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS, $\mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. But $\mathcal{N}_p cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, which implies $\mathcal{N}_p cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is \mathcal{N}_{gp} -CS.

The converse is not true.

Example 3.13. Let $\mathbb{X} = \{na, nb, nc\}$ and the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{S}$, $\mathcal{N}L$ and $\mathcal{N}M$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{N}L = \{\langle nx, (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.4, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.2, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}M = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.3, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.3, f0.6), (t0.7, i0.2, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\},$$

Then the $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}$, $\tau = \{\mathcal{N}0, \mathcal{N}L, \mathcal{N}M, \mathcal{N}1\}$ and the complement of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{S}$ of $\mathcal{N}L$ and $\mathcal{N}M$ are defined as

$$\mathcal{N}\bar{L} = \{\langle nx, (t0.7, i0.7, f0.5), (t0.7, i0.7, f0.4), (t0.7, i0.8, f0.5) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\},$$

$$\mathcal{N}\bar{M} = \{\langle nx, (t0.5, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.7, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.8, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}N = \{\langle nx, (t0.4, i0.8, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.5, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.9, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\}$$

$$\text{If } \mathcal{N}E = \{\langle nx, (t0.5, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.6, i0.3, f0.7), (t0.5, i0.2, f0.7) \rangle \forall nx \in \mathbb{X}\}$$

Here $\mathcal{N}E$ is \mathcal{N}_{gp} -CS but it is not a $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) = \mathcal{N}\bar{M}$ which is not contained in $\mathcal{N}N$.

Theorem 3.14. The union of any two $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) is also a $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{N}E$ and $\mathcal{N}F$ be two $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) . Let \mathcal{V} be a $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS in \mathbb{X} s.t $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ and $\mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. Then, $\mathcal{N}E \cup \mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{V}$.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ and $\mathcal{N}F$ are $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) , implies $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ and $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}F) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. Now, $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E \cup \mathcal{N}F) = \mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \cup \mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}F) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. Thus, $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E \cup \mathcal{N}F) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ whenever $\mathcal{N}E \cup \mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) implies $\mathcal{N}E \cup \mathcal{N}F$ is a $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) .

Theorem 3.15. The intersection of any two $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) is also a $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{N}E$ and $\mathcal{N}F$ be two $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) . Let \mathcal{V} be a $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) s.t $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ and $\mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. Then, $\mathcal{N}E \cap \mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. $\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ and $\mathcal{N}F$ are $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) , implies $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ and $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}F) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. Now, $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E \cap \mathcal{N}F) = \mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \cap \mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}F) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. Thus,

$\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E \cap \mathcal{N}F) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ whenever $\mathcal{N}E \cap \mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) implies $\mathcal{N}E \cap \mathcal{N}F$ is a $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) .

Theorem 3.16. Let $\mathcal{N}E$ be a $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -closed subset of (\mathbb{X}, τ) . If $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E)$, then $\mathcal{N}F$ is also a $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -closed subset of (\mathbb{X}, τ) .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, where \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) . Then $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{N}F$ implies $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. $\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS, $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. Also $\mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E)$ implies $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}F) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E)$. Thus, $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}F) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ and $\mathcal{N}F$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS.

Theorem 3.17. If a set $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) iff $\mathcal{N}_{\alpha}cl(\mathcal{N}E) - \mathcal{N}E$ contains no non-empty $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -CS.

Proof. Necessity: Let $\mathcal{N}F$ be a $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -CS in (\mathbb{X}, τ) such that $\mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) - \mathcal{N}E$. Then $\mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathbb{X} - \mathcal{N}E$. This implies $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathbb{X} - \mathcal{N}F$. Now $\mathbb{X} - \mathcal{N}F$ is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS of (\mathbb{X}, τ) such that $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathbb{X} - \mathcal{N}F$. $\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS then $\mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathbb{X} - \mathcal{N}F$. Thus $\mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathbb{X} - \mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E)$. Now $\mathcal{N}F \subseteq \mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) (\mathbb{X} - \mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E)) = \mathcal{N}0$.

Sufficiency: Assume $\mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) - \mathcal{N}E$ contains no non-empty $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS. Let $\mathcal{N}E \subseteq \mathcal{V}$, \mathcal{V} is $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -OS. Suppose $\mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) \not\subseteq \mathcal{V}$, then $\mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) \cap \mathcal{V}^c$ is a non-empty $\mathcal{N}_{b^*g\alpha}$ -CS of $\mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) - \mathcal{N}E$, which is a contradiction.

$\therefore \mathcal{N}_\alpha cl(\mathcal{N}E) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. Hence $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -CS.

4. $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -Border

Definition 4.1. For any subset $\mathcal{N}E$ of \mathbb{X} , the neutrosophic $ab^*g\alpha$ -border of $\mathcal{N}E$ is defined by $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \mathcal{N}E \setminus \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E)$

Theorem 4.2. In $\mathcal{N}TS(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$, for any subset $\mathcal{N}E$ of \mathbb{X} , the following statements are hold.

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\phi)] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(X)] = \phi$
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}E = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) \cup \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \phi$
- (iv) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) = \mathcal{N}E \setminus \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (v) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]) = \phi$
- (vi) $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -open iff $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \phi$
- (vii) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E))] = \phi$
- (viii) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)])] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (ix) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \mathcal{N}E \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}cl(X \setminus \mathcal{N}E)$

Proof. Statements (i) to (iv) are obvious by the definition of $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -border of $\mathcal{N}E$. If possible, let $nx \in \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)])$.

Then $nx \in \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]$, since $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] \subseteq \mathcal{N}E$, $nx \in \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]) \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E)$.

$\therefore nx \in \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]$, which is the contradiction to (iii). Hence

(v) is proved. $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -open iff $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) = \mathcal{N}E$. But $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \mathcal{N}E \setminus \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E)$ implies $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \phi$.

This proves (vi) & (vii). When $\mathcal{N}E = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]$, then definition of $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -border of $\mathcal{N}E$ becomes $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)])] =$

$\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] \setminus \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)])$.

By using (vii), we get the proof of (viii).

Now, $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \mathcal{N}E \setminus \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) =$

$\mathcal{N}E \cap (\mathbb{X} \setminus \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E)) = \mathcal{N}E \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}cl(\mathbb{X} \setminus \mathcal{N}E)$.

5. $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -Frontier

Definition 5.1. For any subset $\mathcal{N}E$ of \mathbb{X} , the neutrosophic $ab^*g\alpha$ -frontier of $\mathcal{N}E$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \setminus \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E)$$

Theorem 5.2. In $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$, for any subset $\mathcal{N}E$ of \mathbb{X} , the following statements are hold.

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\phi)] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(X)] = \phi$
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] = \phi$
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}cl(\mathcal{N}E)$
- (iv) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) \cup \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}cl(\mathcal{N}E)$
- (v) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) = \mathcal{N}E \setminus \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (vi) If $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -closed iff $\mathcal{N}E = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) \cup \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (vii) $\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E) = \mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)])$
- (viii) If $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -open, then
 $\mathcal{N}E \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] = \phi$
- (ix) $\mathbb{X} = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}cl(\mathcal{N}E) \cup \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}cl(\mathbb{X} \setminus \mathcal{N}E)$
- (x) If $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -open, then
 $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E))] \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (xi) If $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -closed, then
 $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}cl(\mathcal{N}E))] \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (xii) If $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -open iff then
 $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E))] \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) = \phi$

Proof. Statements (i) to (vii) are true by the definition of $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -frontier of $\mathcal{N}E$. By Remark (3.3), If $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -open, $\mathcal{N}E = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E)$ and by statement (ii), $\mathcal{N}E \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] = \phi$. Hence (viii) is proved. (ix) is obvious. Since $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E)$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -open, then $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E) = \mathcal{N}E$, which implies $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha} - \mathcal{N}int(\mathcal{N}E))] \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$. Similarly, (xi) can be proved. By Remark (3.3) and by statement (ii), (xii) is straight forward.

6. Relationship Between $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -Frontier and $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -Border

Theorem 6.1. In $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{X}, \tau)$, for any subset $\mathcal{N}E$ of \mathbb{X} , the following statements are hold.

- (i) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] \setminus \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] = \phi$
- (ii) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (iii) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)])] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (iv) $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)])] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$
- (v) If $\mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -open, then
 $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] \cup \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$

$$(vi) \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]$$

$$(vii) \overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]} \cup \overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]} = \overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]}$$

$$(viii) \overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]} \cap \overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]} = \overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]}$$

Proof. Statement (i) to (iv) are obvious by the definitions of $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -Frontier and $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -border of a set. $\therefore \mathcal{N}E$ is $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -open, then we have a statement from $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -border of a set, $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(E)] = \phi$, which implies $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] \cup \phi = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$. Hence (v) is proved. We know from statement (ii), $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] \subseteq \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]$ which implies $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)] = \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]$. It gives the proof of (vi). By the above statement,

$$\overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]} = \overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)] \cap \mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]}, \text{ and by using De Morgan's law,}$$

$$\overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]} \cap \overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]} =$$

$$\overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}fr(\mathcal{N}E)]} \cup \overline{\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}[\mathcal{N}bd(\mathcal{N}E)]}, \text{ it gives the proof of (vii).}$$

Similarly we can prove the statement (viii).

7. Conclusions

The $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -closed set in $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}$ was defined in this article, and its relationship to other known $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{S}$ in $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}$ was examined. We also introduced and investigated the properties of $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -frontier and $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -border of a set. $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -frontier of a set in $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}$ and found to be connected. A few more functions, including $\mathcal{N}_{ab^*g\alpha}$ -continuous, irresolute functions, can be derived from this set. Furthermore, it can be expanded to include the homeomorphism of $\mathcal{N}\mathcal{T}\mathcal{S}$.

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